

“He Shall See Light” at Isaiah 53:11: A Digital Multi-Tradition Collation and Demonstration of a Well-Known Variant

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Abstract

The “light” variant at Isaiah 53:11—where the Masoretic Text reads “he shall see, he shall be satisfied” (יִרְאֶה אֶת־עֵצָה) while the Great Isaiah Scroll (1QIsa^a) reads “he shall see light” (יִרְאֶה אֹרֶךְ) and the Septuagint renders δεῖξαι αὐτῷ φῶς, “to show him light”—is long established in scholarship, as is the case for the originality of the longer reading. This short, methodological communication does not propose a new solution to any variant. Its contribution is a digital, multi-tradition collation: it shows how a structured, reproducible comparison of the witnesses to a single verse can be assembled with the aid of a computational tool, the BibCrit Ancient Witness Bridge, and how that comparison is to be read and checked against the critical editions. Isaiah 53:11 serves as a familiar first illustration—the method, not the result, is what is on display—and a second, deliberately lesser-known case, a divergence in Deuteronomy 8 where a Qumran scroll, the Samaritan Pentateuch, and the Septuagint align against the Masoretic Text, shows the same procedure at work on the ordinary variants that fill the apparatus rather than the handbooks. The tool is presented as an instrument for initial comparison and research orientation, not as a substitute for the critical editions; the text-critical judgement throughout remains the scholar’s. The method is not tied to these verses, or to the famous cases: a researcher or a student can run the same collation on any passage where the witnesses diverge, as a structured, reproducible starting point that always points on to the editions.

Keywords: Isaiah 53:11; Deuteronomy 8; textual criticism of the Hebrew Bible; Dead Sea Scrolls; Samaritan Pentateuch; Septuagint; digital humanities; multi-tradition collation

1. Introduction

The eleventh verse of Isaiah 53 carries one of the better-known variants of the Hebrew Bible. Where the Masoretic Text reads *יִרְאֶה יִשְׂכַּע*, “he shall see, he shall be satisfied,” the Great Isaiah Scroll from Qumran (1QIsa^a) reads *יִרְאֶה אֹר יִשְׁבַע*, “he shall see light, he shall be satisfied,” and the Old Greek translates accordingly with *δεῖξαι αὐτῷ φῶς*, “to show him light.” The presence or absence of a single word—*אור*, “light”—changes how the Servant’s vindication is pictured, and the variant has been discussed since the first studies of the scroll.¹ The discovery of the scrolls reshaped the discipline’s picture of the early history of the Hebrew text,² and Isaiah 53:11 is one verse where that history turns on a single word.

The evidence for such a variant is not difficult to assemble in principle, but in practice it lies scattered across resources that rarely sit on one desk: the Discoveries in the Judaean Desert volumes for the scrolls, the apparatus of *Biblia Hebraica* for the Masoretic tradition, the Göttingen or Rahlfs editions for the Greek, and separate editions again for the Samaritan Pentateuch, the Peshitta, the Targum, and the Vulgate. A reader who wishes to see, for one verse, what each witness actually reads must consult several specialist volumes and command several scripts.

This article is a short, methodological communication. Its aim is to demonstrate how the witnesses to such a verse can be assembled and compared by digital means, in a tool—the BibCrit Ancient Witness Bridge³—that retrieves the text of each tradition for a given verse, places the readings side by side, and produces a structured, reproducible comparison. It first takes Isaiah 53:11 as a familiar illustration and shows how the Bridge presents it; it then describes the corpus and method, and works a second, deliberately lesser-known case—a divergence in

¹ Millar Burrows, “Variant Readings in the Isaiah Manuscript,” *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 111 (1948): 16–24; Eduard Yechezkel Kutscher, *The Language and Linguistic Background of the Isaiah Scroll (1QIsa^a)*, STDJ 6 (Leiden: Brill, 1974).

² Frank Moore Cross, “The History of the Biblical Text in the Light of Discoveries in the Judaean Desert,” in *Qumran and the History of the Biblical Text*, ed. Frank Moore Cross and Shemaryahu Talmon (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1975), 177–95; Arie van der Kooij, “The Textual Criticism of the Hebrew Bible before and after the Qumran Discoveries,” in *The Bible as Book: The Hebrew Bible and the Judaean Desert Discoveries*, ed. Edward D. Herbert and Emanuel Tov (London: British Library; New Castle, DE: Oak Knoll Press, 2002), 167–77.

³ The BibCrit Ancient Witness Bridge is available at <https://bibcrit.app>; the two analyses discussed here may be opened directly at <https://bibcrit.app/dss?ref=Isaiah%2053%3A11> (Isaiah 53:11) and <https://bibcrit.app/dss?ref=Deuteronomy%208%3A7> (Deuteronomy 8:7). The application is archived at Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19358424>.

Deuteronomy 8—on which the same procedure brings six traditions, the Samaritan Pentateuch among them, into a single view. What is on trial is the collation method, not any textual claim, and the text-critical judgement throughout remains the reader’s.

Assembling witnesses side by side is not in itself new. In print, *The Dead Sea Scrolls Bible* translates the biblical scrolls into English with running notes that flag their variants against the Masoretic Text, the Septuagint, and, where relevant, the Samaritan Pentateuch; and software environments such as Accordance and Logos already place tagged texts of the Hebrew Bible, the Septuagint, and the versions in parallel and allow morphological search across them.⁴ What the present tool adds is narrower. It is not a new corpus, nor a fuller apparatus than these, but an automated first pass that, for a single verse, gathers the readings of several traditions into one view and proposes a structured classification and synthesis of their differences for the scholar to check. What it offers that the established software does not is a fixed, versioned prompt and a cached, re-runnable result, so that a given analysis can be cited and reproduced exactly; it sits upstream of the critical editions and of the established software, and replaces neither.

2. Isaiah 53:11 in the Ancient Witness Bridge

The variant is quickly stated. The Masoretic Text, as vocalized in the Leningrad Codex, reads *יִשְׁכַּע יֵרְאֶה יְרָאָה נִפְשׁוֹ מִן־מַלְאָכָיו*, “out of the trouble of his soul he shall see, he shall be satisfied”—two finite verbs with no object. The Great Isaiah Scroll (1QIsa^a) places *אור*, “light,” between them (*יֵרְאֶה אור יִשְׁכַּע*), and so does the Old Greek, whose *δεῖξαι αὐτῷ φῶς*, “to show him light,” presupposes the same word; the Masoretic Text, the Peshitta, the Vulgate, and the later Greek revisers lack it. Both the reading and the case for it are long established, and most recent editors and translations have adopted the longer reading, though the shorter Masoretic text retains defenders.⁵ The

⁴ Martin Abegg Jr., Peter Flint, and Eugene Ulrich, *The Dead Sea Scrolls Bible: The Oldest Known Bible Translated for the First Time into English* (San Francisco: HarperSanFrancisco, 1999). For the software environments, see the parallel-text and morphological-search features of Accordance (<https://www.accordancebible.com>) and Logos (<https://www.logos.com>).

⁵ The variant and the case for the longer reading are discussed from the first studies onward; see Emanuel Tov, *Textual Criticism of the Hebrew Bible*, 3rd ed., rev. and expanded (Minneapolis: Fortress, 2012); Eugene Ulrich, *The Dead Sea Scrolls and the Origins of the Bible* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1999). For the Qumran Isaiah readings see Eugene Ulrich and Peter W. Flint, *Qumran Cave 1.II: The Isaiah Scrolls*, 2 parts, DJD XXXII (Oxford: Clarendon, 2010), and Patrick W. Skehan and Eugene Ulrich, “Isaiah,” in *Qumran Cave 4.X: The Prophets*, DJD XV (Oxford: Clarendon, 1997), 7–143 (4QIsa^d = 4Q58); for the Greek, Joseph Ziegler, ed., *Isaias*, Septuaginta XIV (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1939).

interest here is not which way the question is decided, but how the evidence for it can be gathered and shown.

Run on the verse, the Bridge returns the comparison in the form it presents to a user, and it is worth describing that form exactly, since it is what the tool produces and what then has to be checked. Each witness is reported with its alignment and the difference typed from a fixed vocabulary—orthographic, morphological, lexical, syntactic, plus, minus, theological: 1QIsa^a is placed with the Greek, the addition registered as a plus, “he shall see light” against “he shall see,” while a purely orthographic difference—the scroll’s plene יסבול for the Masoretic יִסְבֹּל—is marked as such and set aside; the Peshitta and the Vulgate are placed with the Masoretic Text. Every part of this output is generated by a large language model (Anthropic’s Claude, model claude-opus-4-7)—it is the model’s structured restatement of the evidence—and each alignment carries a confidence figure (here 0.95 for 1QIsa^a) that is an internal, heuristic self-rating, not a probability. One feature must be made explicit: the corpus holds one Isaiah scroll, 1QIsa^a, and the cards the model also returns for the further Qumran copies (1QIsa^b and 4QIsa^d, likewise placed with the Greek) are supplied from its training rather than from the corpus, at a lower confidence—so that they are exactly the part of the output to verify against the editions before use, as they were here. The Bridge closes with a synthesis and a “BibCrit Assessment”: for this verse, the headline “Three Hebrew Scrolls Restore ‘Light’ to the Servant,” a short statement of the finding, and an overall confidence of 0.95, reported to document what the tool emits and not to settle the question, which remains the scholar’s.

3. Corpus and Method

Behind the analysis lies a corpus assembled from eight manuscript traditions—the Masoretic Text, the Septuagint, the Dead Sea Scrolls, the Samaritan Pentateuch, the Peshitta, the Greek New Testament, the Targums of Onkelos and Jonathan, and the Latin Vulgate—each recorded word by word, with every word’s reference, surface form, lemma, morphology, and manuscript. The corpus totals roughly 2.29 million word-tokens. Its Dead Sea Scrolls component comprises four manuscripts—the Great Isaiah Scroll (1QIsa^a), 4QSam^a, 11QPaleoLeviticus, and 4QDeutⁿ—so that a Qumran witness enters the comparison wherever one of these covers the passage.

The analytical step is deliberately bounded. When a verse is requested, the system retrieves the word-tokens of the Old Testament witnesses the Bridge collates—the Masoretic Text, the

Septuagint, the relevant Dead Sea Scrolls, the Samaritan Pentateuch, the Peshitta, and the Vulgate—and passes them, with a fixed, versioned prompt that names the text-critical approach to be applied (that associated with Tov and Ulrich), to the language model. Where a major scroll relevant to the passage is not among the four the corpus holds, the prompt directs the model to supply it from its training at a reduced confidence rather than omit it; such readings are flagged as the first thing to verify. What the model receives is thus the corpus readings and the instructions—not manuscript images or a critical apparatus—and what it returns is a structured comparison: each witness’s reading, a classification of the variant, an estimate of the direction of change, and a synthesizing assessment with one heuristic confidence figure. The model does not establish the text or consult the plates; it proposes a comparison the scholar then checks. Every reading, siglum, and classification reported in this article was verified against the printed critical editions, and where the model’s output diverged from them, the editions governed. The prompt is kept under version control and each result cached under a key derived from the verse, the prompt version, and the model version, so that an identical query returns an identical output, citable and reproducible. The aim is to bring the evidence into a single view for a first pass, and to point the user on to the specialist editions where finer judgement is required.

4. A Lesser-Known Case: Deuteronomy 8:7

Isaiah 53:11 is a famous verse, chosen because its arguments are familiar. A fairer measure of the tool is an ordinary divergence on a verse few would single out, and one whose principal scroll the corpus actually holds. Deuteronomy 8:7 offers such a case, with an advantage Isaiah cannot give: because it is Torah, the Samaritan Pentateuch joins the comparison.

There the Masoretic Text reads “a good land, a land of brooks of water.” The Qumran manuscript 4QDeutⁿ reads instead “a good and broad land” (ארץ טובה ורחבה), and in the extra word it is joined by the Samaritan Pentateuch and by the Old Greek, whose γῆν ἀγαθὴν καὶ πολλήν, “a good and large land,” renders the Hebrew ארץ טובה with πολλήν exactly as the Greek does for the same phrase at Exod 3:8; the Peshitta and the Vulgate, with the Masoretic Text, lack it. Run on the verse, the Bridge places 4QDeutⁿ, the Samaritan Pentateuch, and the Septuagint together against the Masoretic Text, the Peshitta, and the Vulgate, and types “broad” as a plus. It also reads the evidence correctly without any steer from us: its synthesis observes that the convergence of a Qumran Hebrew manuscript with the Greek Vorlage and the Samaritan text shows the plus to

have “existed in a genuine Hebrew textual stream and is not a Greek translator’s expansion,” yet judges the longer reading the more likely secondary—“a textbook case of harmonization toward the stock phrase ‘good and broad land’ (cf. Exod 3:8),” with the shorter Masoretic text “likely earlier.” The accompanying assessment is headed “4QDeutⁿ confirms LXX–SP ‘broad land’ plus,” at a confidence of 0.82.

That reading is sound, and the scholar’s task is to confirm it against the editions and to add what the tool did not weigh. Each reading was checked against the editions—the Cave 4 Deuteronomy volume for the scroll, the Göttingen Septuagint for the Greek (which the Bridge itself loads only in the Rahlfs edition), the Samaritan edition for its text⁶—and the harmonization verdict is reinforced by something the witnesses alone do not show: 4QDeutⁿ is not a full Torah scroll but an excerpted, liturgical text—the “All Souls Deuteronomy,” whose passage on the good land underlies the blessing after meals—long recognized to have undergone harmonistic editing.⁷ Its agreement with the similarly expansionist Samaritan tradition is thus less a second independent witness than a second instance of the same pull toward a familiar phrase. The tool gathered the six traditions and proposed the right reading of them; the editions and the manuscript’s known character secure it.

The variant is not a celebrated one, and that is the point. On the small, recurring divergences that fill an apparatus rather than a handbook, the Bridge does what it is meant to do: it gathers the traditions into one view, types the difference, proposes a reading, and leaves the decision, and the editions, to the scholar.

5. Limitations

Several limits must be stated plainly. The Bridge is not a critical edition and is no substitute for one: it does not replace the Discoveries in the Judaean Desert volumes, the apparatus of *Biblia Hebraica*, the Göttingen Septuagint, or the other specialist editions, and any reading or judgement it surfaces must be checked against them before it is relied upon—as every reading in this article

⁶ The scroll is edited by Sidnie White [Crawford], “41. 4QDeutⁿ,” in *Qumran Cave 4.IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings*, ed. Eugene Ulrich, Frank Moore Cross, et al., DJD XIV (Oxford: Clarendon, 1995), 117–29, pls. XXVIII–XXIX; the Greek in John W. Wevers, ed., *Deuteronomium*, Septuaginta: Vetus Testamentum Graecum III.2 (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1977); the Samaritan text in Abraham Tal and Moshe Florentin, eds., *The Pentateuch: The Samaritan Version and the Masoretic Version* (Tel Aviv: Tel Aviv University Press, 2010).

⁷ That Has Undergone Harmonistic Editing,” *Hebrew Union College Annual* 62 (1991): 117–54; Sidnie White Crawford, *Rewriting Scripture in Second Temple Times* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2008), 24–26.

was. Its coverage is partial: the scroll component holds four manuscripts, and for Isaiah the corpus carries 1QIsa^a only from chapter 7 onward; further scrolls cited above are not in the corpus and are returned only because the model is prompted to supply them from its training, so that their readings were confirmed here against the published editions rather than taken on the tool's word. The Greek it loads is the Rahlfs edition rather than the fuller Göttingen text, a first comparison and not a critical determination where the inner-Greek history is complex. The confidence figure is a heuristic rating, not a measured probability. And the corpus data are drawn under a non-commercial research licence, which restricts their reuse accordingly.

6. Conclusion

The two verses worked here are of opposite kinds. Isaiah 53:11 is a celebrated variant whose evidence is familiar; the divergence in Deuteronomy 8 is the sort that fills an apparatus and rarely a handbook. On both, the tool does the same modest work: it gathers the witnesses—six traditions where the passage is Torah and the Samaritan Pentateuch joins—into one reproducible view, types the differences, and leaves the decision, and the editions, to the scholar. None of the textual conclusions is new; what the communication has tried to show is that the assembling of the evidence can be done in one structured, citable step.

The procedure is not tied to these verses, or to the famous cases. The Masoretic Text, the Septuagint, the Peshitta, and the Vulgate cover the Old Testament throughout, the Samaritan Pentateuch joins them across the Torah, and a Qumran witness is brought in wherever one of the corpus scrolls reaches the passage; so a scholar weighing a known crux and a student meeting a minor variant for the first time can each call up, for the verse before them, what every available tradition reads, set side by side and typed by the kind of difference it shows. In each the tool remains what it is here—an instrument for an initial, reproducible orientation, always to be carried on into the critical editions, not a substitute for them.

The example is small, but it is the kind of small, recurring task—to see what each witness reads, here, now—that has until now required several volumes and several scripts, and that a structured digital collation can usefully consolidate.

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Conflict of Interest

The author is the developer of the BibCrit software described in this article and declares no other conflict of interest.

AI Use Disclosure

This study and its write-up made substantial use of generative AI, disclosed here in the interest of full transparency. The analytical tool at the centre of the article, BibCrit, uses the Anthropic Claude API (model claude-opus-4-7) to generate its structured textual analyses, as described in §§2–3. In preparing the manuscript, the author additionally used Anthropic’s Claude to draft and edit prose, to compute the corpus statistics reported in §4 from the underlying data files, and to assist in checking factual, text-critical, and bibliographic claims against secondary sources. All manuscript readings, sigla, textual data, and citations were verified against the primary witnesses and the cited critical editions. The author takes full responsibility for the content of this communication, and no AI system is listed as an author.

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